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ПОЛУЧАВАНЕ НА МИНОРНИ АКТИНИДИ В РЕАКТОРИ С ВОДА ПОД НАЛЯГАНЕ (III) – ИЗПОЛЗВАНЕ НА РЕМИКС ГОРИВО

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MINOR ACTINIDES PRODUCTION IN PRESSURISED WATER REACTORS (III) – REMIX FUEL USAGE

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Минорните актиниди имат дял около 0,1 w% в нуклидният инвентар на отработеното гориво от реактори с вода под налягане. Въпреки това, в дългосрочен план те допринасят за около 3/4 от остатъчното енергоотделяне. REMIX е вид смесено уран-плутониево гориво, разработено в Русия за експлоатация в реактори от типа ВВЕР. В настоящата статия е разгледано получаването на минорни актиниди при експлоатацията на REMIX горива.

Introduction

Previously, comprehensive analyses on minor actinides' accumulation in pressurised water reactors' spent fuel as a function of the fuel type and its cooling time had been carried out. The fuel types taken into consideration were regular UO_2 fuel with different initial enrichment and burn-up and a variety of MOX fuels. The results can be found in [1-4].

Figure 1. General flowchart of fissile materials in REMIX fuel cycle with parallel operation of thermal and fast reactors [5]

REMIX is a novel nuclear fuel aimed at providing alternative means for nuclear fuel cycle closure using WWER nuclear reactor. The concept is Russian and can be employed for single or multiple recycling of uranium and plutonium in PWR, with or without introducing fast reactors in

the fuel cycle scheme. This fuel is developed as an alternative to classic MOX usage in WWER reactors. The fuel design and its isotopic compositions are such that they ensure full WWER core loading without changes in reactor and core design and keep the existing safety margins. This fuel type is manufactured from uranium-plutonium regenerate extracted from spent WWER nuclear fuel with addition of various fissile materials – re-enriched uranium tails, highly enriched uranium or plutonium from nuclear warheads decommissioning, bred ^{233}U or plutonium extracted from fast reactor blankets, etc. The uranium-plutonium regenerate itself represents the uranium-plutonium mixture recovered from the spent WWER fuel with removed minor actinides and fission products. In this kind of radiochemical reprocessing the uranium and plutonium do not represent separate material streams as it is in commercial PUREX reprocessing. In the case of multiple recycling, the regenerate can be produced by extracting the uranium and plutonium that had left in the spent REMIX fuel from the previous loading [5-8]. The overall scheme of nuclear fuel cycle in the general case of operating simultaneously thermal and fast reactors is shown on Figure 1.

Input data

In the current article four varieties of REMIX fuel isotopic compositions are examined. They represent four consecutive recycles, each using uranium-plutonium regenerate from the previous loading. The first REMIX fuel uses a regenerate from spent WWER-1000 UO_2 fuel with initial enrichment of 4.26% and burn-up of 49 200 MWd/tU. In order to provide reactivity margin, the regenerate had been blended with depleted uranium (99.9% ^{238}U) and weapons-grade highly enriched uranium (93% ^{235}U). The isotopic compositions are listed in Table 1 and are sourced from [7]. The analysis has been done using the ORIGEN module of the SCALE6.1 software package [9]. The evolution of minor actinides' concentration as a function of spent fuel's cooling time has been considered because that would give information about their nuclide inventory if reprocessing takes place by the 300th year of cooling. To achieve results comparability, the reactor parameters are the same as in [1-4] – 1000 MW electric power output, 85% capacity factor, and 32.8% gross thermodynamic efficiency.

Table 1. REMIX fuel initial isotopic compositions, g/tHM [7]

	REMIX 1	REMIX 2	REMIX 3	REMIX 4
^{234}U	1.66	7.87	20	30
^{235}U	40 540	42 350	43 820	44 990
^{236}U	5510	9440	12 870	15 960
^{238}U	942 730	932 990	926 000	920 420
^{238}Pu	300	710	1060	1340
^{239}Pu	5930	7260	7920	8360
^{240}Pu	2860	3710	4100	4310
^{241}Pu	1340	1930	2190	2340
^{242}Pu	800	1610	2060	2290

Results and analysis

The burn-up achieved with the four REMIX fuel compositions has been calculated as 48 647 MWd/tHM. The minor actinides' concentrations are listed in Tables 2-4. In order to evaluate the REMIX fuel usage's effects from the point of view of minor actinides, the results are compared with results for UO_2 (UOX) and MOX fuel. The calculations for UOX have been carried out for TBC-M fuel assembly type which has design enrichment of 4.31% and design burn-up of 49 000 MWd/tHM [10]. It has been selected because the burn-up is similar to that calculated for the REMIX fuel and has also been analysed in [4]. The minor actinides' concentrations for mixed uranium-plutonium fuel are determined for fuel containing 5% plutonium and with the following isotopic composition – ^{238}Pu – 0.046%, ^{239}Pu – 3.091%, ^{240}Pu – 1.110%, ^{241}Pu – 0.548%, ^{242}Pu – 0.205%, ^{238}U – 94.715%, and ^{235}U – 0.285%. This fuel type has been analysed in [3,4]. In order to obtain results comparability, the MOX fuel is irradiated to 49 000 MWd/tHM in a standard 17x17 PWR fuel assembly.

Table 2. Total neptunium concentration as a function of cooling time, g/tHM

	0.10	0.30	1.00	3.00	10.00	30.00	100.00	300.00
	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y
REMIX 1	1198.01	1200.00	1200.00	1201.00	1208.00	1251.00	1466.00	2003.00
REMIX 2	1579.01	1581.00	1581.00	1582.00	1590.00	1637.00	1874.00	2464.00
REMIX 3	1914.01	1917.00	1917.00	1918.00	1926.00	1976.00	2228.00	2854.00
REMIX 4	2216.01	2219.00	2219.00	2220.00	2229.00	2281.00	2543.00	3197.00

Table 3. Total americium concentration as a function of cooling time, g/tHM

	0.10	0.30	1.00	3.00	10.00	30.00	100.00	300.00
	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y
REMIX 1	808.85	830.25	903.48	1098.97	1647.15	2457.60	2741.35	2198.93
REMIX 2	1121.62	1145.10	1225.45	1439.14	2040.91	2929.65	3238.46	2638.17
REMIX 3	1280.90	1305.81	1391.06	1618.75	2255.82	3198.75	3524.53	2886.20
REMIX 4	1359.72	1385.68	1474.54	1711.84	2375.90	3358.82	3698.58	3032.22

Table 4. Total curium concentration as a function of cooling time, g/tHM

	0.10	0.30	1.00	3.00	10.00	30.00	100.00	300.00
	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y
REMIX 1	516.15	506.85	484.37	446.19	348.21	177.89	39.87	29.15
REMIX 2	728.01	716.08	686.15	633.09	494.02	252.52	56.69	41.51
REMIX 3	819.11	805.99	772.80	713.20	556.50	284.28	63.62	46.52
REMIX 4	853.63	839.86	805.15	743.06	579.83	295.99	65.99	48.18

The concentrations of neptunium, americium, and curium as a function of cooling time for both uranium and mixed uranium-plutonium fuels are given in Table 5. The analysis shows increasing concentrations for neptunium, americium, and curium in any given point in time with each subsequent REMIX fuel recycle. That is an expected result given the increase in the plutonium mass and its isotopic composition deterioration with each recycle.

The change of minor actinides' total mass concentrations in REMIX fuel follows known patterns that had already been examined. With regards to the comparison to uranium and MOX fuels the received results are not unexpected – the minor actinides' concentrations are higher with respect to UOX fuel and lower (except for neptunium after 100 years for REMIX 3 and 4) with respect to MOX fuel. That is direct effect of the initial plutonium loading. The total mass of the minor actinides is shown on Figure 1.

Table 5. Total minor actinides concentration as a function of cooling time for UOX (TBC-M) and MOX fuels, g/tHM

Minor Actinide	Fuel Type	0.10	0.30	1.00	3.00	10.00	30.00	100.00	300.00
		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y
Np	UOX	721.41	722.70	722.80	723.30	728.60	761.70	929.60	1348.00
	MOX	187.61	187.90	188.30	190.50	211.00	338.00	978.80	2574.00
Am	UOX	247.39	264.12	321.38	474.39	902.98	1537.65	1762.08	1345.87
	MOX	1431.54	1494.84	1711.43	2290.10	3911.80	6309.54	7149.80	5556.67
Cm	UOX	97.83	94.95	88.65	80.62	62.65	31.48	6.21	4.26
	MOX	1073.11	1050.40	997.73	919.25	728.29	396.83	127.70	105.91

Figure 1. Total mass of minor actinides in different fuels, g/tHM

Conclusion

Given that plutonium is loaded with the fresh fuel, higher concentrations of minor actinides with respect to uranium fuel are to be expected. It is evident that the results of the current study agree very well with those expectations. However, concentrations of americium and curium are lower than their respective concentrations in MOX fuel. Moreover, those concentrations are lower after fourth recycle in REMIX fuel cycle than after only one recycle in classic MOX fuel (the selected MOX fuel for this comparison has relatively low plutonium concentration with higher concentration of even isotopes).

Concerning the total concentration of minor actinides, it is higher after the second REMIX recycle up to the third year compared to MOX, but in long-term perspective it is significantly lower (25% to 50%) even after multiple recycling. Alongside other positive effects, the present results show that the REMIX concept could be a viable option for WWER fuel cycle closure.

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